

Open-LBP-RF: A Clinical Note Dataset annotated with Lower Back Pain Risk Factors

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Abstract

Choosing Wisely Canada identifies six red-flag risk factors that justify imaging for patients with lower back pain (LBP), yet existing datasets for studying these indicators remain publicly inaccessible, small, and manually annotated. We present Open-LBP-RF, the first publicly available clinical note dataset annotated for LBP imaging risk factors. Our annotations are generated using a structured prompting framework called R2D2-G (Role-play, Domain, Rules, Output format, Demonstration, Guidance), which guides large language models (LLMs) to label risk factors using chain-of-thought rationales in structured JSON format. We demonstrate that R2D2-G achieves a competitive weighted F1-score (0.89) on zero-shot risk factor classification on an expert-annotated set. Qualitative analysis shows it uncovers both valid clinical mentions and human labeling errors. We release the Open-LBP-RF dataset and the novel R2D2-G prompting framework to facilitate further work on LLM-based clinical annotation and risk-aware triage for lower back pain. Given the importance of public clinical annotations, our approach represents a path from prompt calibration on internal data to public dataset annotation at scale. Our dataset is available at: <https://huggingface.co/datasets/Aman-J/OPEN-LBP-RF>.

Keywords

Lower Back pain, Imaging risk factors, Clinical NLP dataset, Clinical note annotation,

1. Introduction

Lower back pain (LBP) is among the most common disabilities worldwide, affecting 13% of adults in the U.S. and over half of chronic pain sufferers in Canada [1, 2, 3]. Prevalence estimates range from 1.4% to 15.6% across studies [4]. Imaging (e.g., X-rays, CT scans, MRIs) is generally discouraged unless red flags are present, as unnecessary tests expose patients to harm and increase costs [5, 6, 7]. Clinical guidelines from Choosing Wisely Canada enumerate six such risk factors: a history of cancer, unexplained weight loss, recent infection, fever, loss of bowel or bladder control, and neurological deficits such as Abnormal reflexes, or loss of muscle power or feeling in the legs [5]. Despite these guidelines, imaging overuse for LBP remains prevalent [8].

Developing machine learning models that can identify these risk factors from clinical notes is challenging due to the lack of public datasets. Prior work [9] relied on manually annotated expert datasets, which were costly to produce, imbalanced, and restricted in access. To address this, we introduce **Open-LBP-RF**, the first open-access dataset of clinical notes annotated for LBP imaging risk factors. This dataset is aggregated and filtered from a collection of open-source and credentialed clinical datasets. Annotations are generated using **R2D2-G**, a structured prompting framework for clinical annotations that leverages large language models (LLMs) to provide label predictions with explicit reasoning.

Our contributions are:

- We introduce Open-LBP-RF, the first public dataset of clinical notes annotated for LBP imaging risk factors.

Challenge and Workshop (BC9): Large Language Models for Clinical and Biomedical NLP, International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI), August 16–22, 2025, Montreal, Canada

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- We design R2D2-G, a reusable prompting framework that enables LLMs to output interpretable labels with reasoning chains.
- We evaluate R2D2-G on an expert-annotated dataset and show it achieves competitive performance in a zero-shot setting (weighted F1 = 0.89).
- We conduct a qualitative error analysis, identifying both model limitations and human annotation inconsistencies.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 covers background on LLM prompting. Section 3 describes our dataset construction and R2D2-G method. Section 4 presents the evaluation and error analysis, followed by the conclusion in Section 5.

2. Background

Large language models (LLMs) such as GPT [10, 11], LLaMA [12, 13], Mistral [14], and Gemma [15] have demonstrated strong multitask abilities by training on large-scale corpora using an autoregressive objective. In addition to modeling language, these models capture general knowledge and can be adapted to downstream tasks with minimal task-specific tuning [16, 17, 18].

Recent work has explored the potential of prompt-based learning, where pretrained LLMs are conditioned via task-specific prompts rather than fine-tuning [19]. This has proven particularly effective in domains like biomedical NLP, where labeled data is scarce. Few-shot prompting (providing labeled examples) and chain-of-thought prompting (breaking reasoning into steps) [20], when designed carefully, enable LLMs to perform well on complex reasoning and classification tasks [21, 22].

In clinical NLP, prompting has been used for entity extraction, question answering, and relation labeling with promising results [23, 24]. Medical LLMs exhibit inconsistent and unpredictable errors when applied to clinical tasks, often diverging from human reasoning [25]. To address this, structured prompting frameworks that include task rules, demonstrations, and reasoning expectations have gained attention. Our work builds on these trends by formalizing R2D2-G, a structured prompting framework that combines instruction-following, domain grounding, and reasoning to generate interpretable, label-rich annotations. We demonstrate its utility in constructing the first open dataset for LBP imaging risk factors.

3. Methodology

We designed our prompting pipeline with the understanding that clinical notes differ widely in language, structure, and diagnostic richness depending on their source. To ensure robustness and generalizability of the downstream dataset, we selected a mixture of datasets — synthetic patient notes and de-identified clinical discharge notes — each filtered for LBP relevance. This ensured both linguistic variety and clinical relevance. The following sections detail our data curation process and annotation framework.

3.1. Data Curation

We curated data from three sources: (1) synthetic notes from Asclepius [26], (2) de-identified electronic health records from MIMIC-IV [27], and (3) PubMed Central-derived patient summaries [28]. To identify notes relevant to lower back pain (LBP), we applied keyword filtering (e.g., "lower back pain") and manual inspection. Statistics before and after filtering are provided in Table 1.

3.2. R2D2-G: A Meta-Prompting Framework

We introduce **R2D2-G**, a prompting framework composed of six components: **Role-play**, **Domain context**, **Rules**, **Output format**, **Demonstration**, and **Guidance** (See Figure 1). Each component provides

Table 1

Description of clinical note datasets: This table presents the original counts of the clinical notes and the counts after filtering for the keyword “lower back pain.”

Source	Description	Counts (#notes)	LBP Notes
PMC-Patients [28]	Consists of 167,034 patient notes that were curated from PubMed Central (PMC).	167,034	821
Asclepius - synthetic clinical notes [26]	A collection synthetic clinical notes generated using GPT-3.5 turbo.	158,114	673
MIMIC-IV Clinical Notes [27]	Contains 331,794 de-identified discharge summaries from 145,915 patients admitted to the hospital and emergency department at the Beth Israel Deaconess Medical Center in Boston, MA, USA.	331,794	6,295

Figure 1: Schematic of the R2D2-G meta-prompting framework for auto-labeling lower back pain (LBP) imaging risk factors using LLMs. The meta-prompt composes five parts, Role-play, Domain Information, Rules, Output Formatting, and Demonstration, that define the structure of the final prompt. A Guidance Prompt is appended per sample to initiate the generation. The prompt, combined with a clinical note, is used to generate labels via LLM inference and JSON parsing.

distinct semantic scaffolding to guide large language models (LLMs) to extract red-flag risk factors from clinical text. Formally, the meta-prompt structure is defined as:

$$\text{Meta-Prompt } (P) = R; D; R; O; D; G$$

Where (;) refers to concatenation. Given a clinical note N , the LLM is queried with the composed meta-prompt P as:

$$\text{LLM}(P \oplus N) \rightarrow \text{Risk Factor Labels} + \text{Rationales}$$

Following Kong et al. [29], we first prime the LLM to act as a clinical reviewer via a role-play instruction. We subsequently concatenate domain information containing LBP risk-factor definitions and their specific inclusion/exclusion criteria. Inspired by Zeng et al. [30], we then explicitly enumerate task rules to improve adherence. The output format component conditions structured JSON generation, while the demonstration section shows how to apply the rules using examples. Finally, a guidance string appended after the clinical note triggers the full generation process. Details of each prompt segment are available in Appendix A. R2D2-G is an additive prompting strategy and can be combined with test-time inference techniques like self-consistency [31], reflexion [32], and self-refine [33] to further improve accuracy, at the cost of additional compute.

Annotation Pipeline. Once the meta-prompt is constructed, it is paired with a clinical note to form a complete input sequence. This prompt-note combination is passed to an instruction-tuned language model – in our case, Mistral-Instruct-v0.3 [14] – for generation of identified risk factors. The expected

output is a structured JSON object containing binary labels for each of the six red-flag risk factors, along with corresponding chain-of-thought rationales (Detailed in Figure 7 of Appendix A). If the model returns valid JSON, the output is accepted directly. Otherwise, we fall back to multinomial sampling and retry up to four times. We find that all generations yielded a parseable output within two attempts.

The final Open-LBP-RF dataset comprises 7,789 clinical notes annotated using the R2D2-G framework. Each instance includes binary labels for six red-flag imaging risk factors, along with corresponding chain-of-thought rationales. Figure 2 summarizes the frequency of risk factor assignments across the annotated corpus.

Figure 2: Risk factor distribution of lower back pain in OPEN-LBP-RF. **Disclaimer:** Not all notes originate from outpatient or primary care settings. The Choosing Wisely recommendation regarding imaging for lower back pain applies only to primary care and outpatient visits.

4. Evaluation and Discussion

To assess the quality of R2D2-G-generated annotations, we evaluated its performance on an expert-labeled dataset [9] from the Manitoba Centre for Health Policy (MCHP). Since our prompts use only a single demonstration, the evaluation setting effectively qualifies as zero-shot. We report quantitative results for both binary and multi-label classification settings, followed by a qualitative analysis of errors. We report standard classification metrics, precision, recall, and F1 score.

Binary Classification We first assess the model’s ability to detect whether a clinical note contains at least one red-flag risk factor. This “risk-factor presence detection” setting treats the task as a binary classification problem (any risk vs. none). Table 2 summarizes the model’s performance on the MCHP dataset. R2D2-G achieved a weighted F1-score of 0.89, which is notable given the zero-shot evaluation setting.

Multi-label Classification We also evaluate per-label performance to determine how well R2D2-G identifies each of the six risk factors. Results in Table 3 show strong performance for risk factors like *cancer* and *abnormal reflexes* ($F1 = 0.72$ for both). In contrast, performance was notably lower for *infection* ($F1 = 0.04$), which involved numerous false positives. The *weight loss* class exhibited a particularly high false-negative rate, with 28 of 32 positive cases missed.

Table 2

Classification performance metrics for identifying risk factors using R2D2-G framework on MCHP dataset [9]. We report the precision, recall, f1-score, macro and weighted average of correctly identifying a note with a risk factor.

Category	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
No Risk Factor	0.97	0.89	0.93	2402
Risk Factor	0.50	0.80	0.62	347
Accuracy			0.88	2749
Macro Avg	0.74	0.84	0.77	2749
Weighted Avg	0.91	0.88	0.89	2749

Table 3

Comprehensive results of the automatic annotation with R2D2-G approach on the MCHP dataset [9]. The support refers to the number of positive occurrence of the risk-factor.

	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support	False Positive	False Negative
Cancer	0.58	0.96	0.72	53	37	2
Weight	0.40	0.12	0.19	32	6	28
Fever	0.33	0.82	0.47	17	28	3
Infection	0.02	0.33	0.04	9	137	6
Bowel	0.33	0.56	0.42	9	10	4
Abreflex	0.63	0.83	0.72	236	117	39
Micro Avg	0.45	0.77	0.57	356	-	-
Macro Avg	0.38	0.61	0.43	356	-	-
Weighted Avg	0.56	0.77	0.63	356	-	-

Qualitative Error Analysis To further examine the causes of classification errors, we performed a qualitative review of a subset of 50 misclassified examples—five false positives and five false negatives for each of the six risk factors. The R2D2-G framework generates explicit chain-of-thought rationales for each predicted label, which we can leverage for interpretability. A clinical expert (AK) reviewed each misclassified example along with the model’s rationale and the ground truth label. Surprisingly, 22 of the 50 reviewed cases were found to reflect inconsistencies or omissions in the original expert annotations rather than model error. Table 4 summarizes six distinct categories of human annotation error, including misinterpretation of risk-factor findings and failure to apply exclusion criteria consistently. The categorization of human labeling errors can serve as a valuable resource to guide experts and AI in subsequent labeling tasks. Among the remaining 28 errors attributed to the model (Table 5), 13 involved the failure to exclude risk factors unrelated to lower back pain—such as those stemming from falls, chronic illness, or surgical complications. Another significant subset (12) resulted from the model failing to follow explicit instructions outlined in the exclusion criteria.

Expert Validation of a subset of Open-LBP-RF To directly assess annotation quality in Open-LBP-RF, we sampled 60 clinical notes (20 per source) and presented them to a clinical expert (AK) for verification. Table 6 reports the F1-score and Cohen’s Kappa for each red flag. We observe a macro F1-score of 92% and an average Cohen’s Kappa of 90%, indicating a high agreement between generated labels and expert judgment.

4.1. Discussion

Our evaluation highlights both the strengths and limitations of R2D2-G as a prompting framework for clinical note annotation. In the binary setting, the model performs robustly in detecting the presence of any red-flag risk factor, and in the multi-label setting, it achieves high F1-scores for classes such as cancer and abnormal reflexes. Performance degrades for certain risk factors like infection and weight loss. Our analysis suggests that some of these errors could be mitigated through more precise domain-specific instructions. A key insight from our qualitative analysis is that nearly half of the

Table 4
Categorization of Expert Labeling Errors

Name	Description	Count
"Abnormal" vs. "Absent" reflexes	Misinterpretation of reflex status, where "abnormal" was mistakenly classified as "absent."	2
Missed exclusion criteria	Invalid cases were incorrectly included due to overlooked exclusion criteria.	4
Missed inclusion criteria	A valid case was excluded due to missed inclusion criteria.	1
Missed risk factor	A risk factor was present but was overlooked by the human expert.	3
Incorrectly marked as positive	A risk factor was marked as present when none was found.	6
New exclusion criteria	Errors were made because new exclusion criteria were not specified in the pre-defined instructions to expert annotators.	6

Table 5
Categorization of Model Errors.

Name	Description	Count
Wrong Label Mapping	Model outputs are not mapped to True/False.	1
Instruction Not Followed	Model fails to follow the specified instructions. This can range from not invalidating cases that satisfy the exclusion criteria. Majority of these were of the form that UTI is not a relevant infection.	12
Underspecified Prompt	Model required more specifications for certain risk factors, such as reflex being absent as opposed to abnormal, and pain having improved.	2
Low Back Pain Pertinence	The risk factors are not pertinent to lower back pain. For example, the onset of risk factors is due to other conditions like falls or chronic conditions, or incontinence caused by surgery.	13

Table 6
Expert Validation of Open-LBP-RF.

	Cancer	Weight	Fever	Infection	Bowel	Abreflex	Micro Avg
Support	21	0	9	18	5	21	74
F1-Score	0.92	-	1.00	0.85	0.89	0.95	0.92
Cohen's Kappa	0.88	-	1.00	0.79	0.88	0.92	0.90

examined model "errors" were attributed to inconsistencies or oversights in the expert-provided ground truth. This supports recent findings that LLMs can help surface hidden issues in human annotations and act as valuable second-opinion reviewers [34, 25]. The explicit rationales generated by R2D2-G not only aid interpretability but also offer a mechanism for systematic error analysis and label auditing.

5. Conclusion

We present Open-LBP-RF, the first publicly available clinical note dataset annotated for imaging-relevant lower back pain red-flag risk factors. To create this resource, we introduce R2D2-G, a modular prompting framework that guides large language models to generate structured, interpretable annotations with chain-of-thought rationales. Evaluation on an expert-labeled dataset demonstrates strong zero-shot performance for several risk factors, while also revealing class-specific variability, highlighting both the utility and limitations of LLM-based annotation in clinical NLP. Qualitative analysis further reveals the potential of LLMs to surface inconsistencies in human labels, reinforcing their role as second-opinion annotators. We release the dataset and prompting template to support reproducible research in weak supervision, prompt design, and clinically grounded information extraction.

Acknowledgments

We acknowledge the support of the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC) and the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR). This research was made possible, in part, by the assistance provided by ACENET (ace-net.ca) and the Digital Research Alliance of Canada (alliancecan.ca).

Declaration on Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used Grammarly for: Grammar and spelling check. Further, the author(s) used GPT-4o to: Generate literature review. After using these tool(s)/service(s), the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the publication's content.

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A. Prompts

Role-playing Prompt: You are acting as a medical expert tasked with reviewing a clinical note to identify any of the six "red flags" or risk factors that would justify the need for immediate X-ray imaging tests for a patient experiencing lower back pain. Follow the rules and return the findings in a structured JSON format.

Figure 3: Role playing prompt for "Clinical Note Annotator AI".

Risk-factor descriptions: ### The Six Red Flags or Risk Factors are as follows with brief definitions:

1. **History of Cancer**: Indicate if the patient has a confirmed history of cancer (e.g., previous diagnosis of any type of cancer). Example: "The patient was diagnosed with breast cancer five years ago."
2. **Unexplained Weight Loss**: Any significant unintentional weight loss within a short period that cannot be attributed to a known cause (e.g., diet, exercise). Example: "The patient reports losing 10 pounds over the past month without dieting."
3. **Fever**: Any report of fever, especially if persistent or unexplained (e.g., fever without accompanying flu symptoms). Example: "The patient has had a low-grade fever for the last two weeks."
4. **Recent Infection**: A recent history of infections, particularly those involving the spine or systemic infections (recent typically refers to the past few weeks to months). Example: "The patient had a urinary tract infection two weeks ago."
5. **Loss of Bowel or Bladder Control**: Any loss of control or change in bowel or bladder function (e.g., new onset incontinence). Example: "The patient is experiencing incontinence."
6. **Abnormal Reflexes, or Loss of Muscle Power or Feeling in the Legs**: Any indications of neurological deficits like numbness, tingling, or weakness in the legs. Example: "The patient has a tingling sensation in the left leg and reduced muscle strength."

Figure 4: LBP risk-factor descriptions used in the auto-labeling prompt. We use markdown to emphasize the risk-factor descriptions to the LLM. This helps to condition the LLM on relevant domain information.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: ### Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for Red Flags:

Inclusion criteria:

- Lower extremities for loss of muscle function
- Positive straight leg test
- Nerve impingement
- Sciatica, but need to confirm radiculopathy
- Incontinence related to a nerve issue
- If back pain has improved
- Follow-up discussions of imaging results
- Saddle anesthesia
- Notes that do not specify upper vs. lower back p

Exclusion criteria:

- HIV is not a relevant infection (regardless of viral load and strain/location)
- Urinary symptoms other than incontinence are neither risk factors nor symptoms of relevant infection
- Shingles as an infection if it is a lumbar dermatome
- Nocturnal enuresis
- Degenerative diseases or osteoarthritis with an indication of back pain
- Copy/pasted imaging results onto the electronic medical record note
- Notes that mention previous or resolved back pain

Figure 5: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria. We use markdown to emphasize the inclusion and exclusion criterias to the LLM.

Rules: ### RULES TO FOLLOW:

1. Read the provided clinical note carefully.
2. Identify and list any of the above six red flags or risk factors explicitly mentioned in the note.
3. Pay close attention to the specific red flags or risk factors listed above and to the inclusion and exclusion criteria.
4. Only include findings that explicitly match the risk-factors.
5. Avoid inferring or assuming information not clearly stated in the clinical note.
6. Return your findings in the specified JSON format:

```
“ “ json
{
  "step-by-step thought for history_of_cancer":
  "Your thought process for assigning the history_of_cancer label.",
  "history_of_cancer": "False" or "True",
.
.
.
.
}
“ “
END
```

Figure 6: Rules instruction for annotations. We enforce the language model to output 'JSON' structure using keys and textual description of the keys. Explicit instructions for JSON encoding conditions the LLM to return the output in the defined signature.

Demonstration: ****For example:****

Clinical Note: Patient reports experiencing lower back pain that started two weeks ago. The pain is severe and radiates to the left leg. The patient reports a sudden, significant unintentional weight loss over the past month and has recently noticed a loss of sensation in the foot.

```
```json
{
 "C-O-T Risk": "No indication of cancer history is mentioned in the note.",
 "history_of_cancer": "False",

 "C-O-T Risk": "The patient reports a sudden, significant unintentional
weight
loss over the past month.",
 "unexplained_weight_loss": "True",

 "C-O-T Risk": "There is no mention of fever in the note.",
 "fever": "False",

 "C-O-T Risk": "There is no mention of a recent infection in the note.",
 "recent_infection": "False",

 "C-O-T Risk": "There is no mention of loss of bowel or bladder control in the
note.",
 "loss_of_bowel_or_bladder_control": "False",

 "C-O-T Risk": "The note mentions a loss of sensation in the foot,
which qualifies for this category.",
 "abnormal_reflexes_or_loss_of_muscle_power_or_feeling_in_legs": "True"
}
```
END
```

Figure 7: Initial demonstration prompt. We generated a demonstration using the previous prompt for the initial dataset annotation. 'C-O-T Risk' expands to 'step-by-step thought for {risk}', where risk can be history_of_cancer, loss_of_bowel_or_bladder_control, abnormal_reflexes_or_loss_of_muscle_power_or_feeling_in_legs, recent_infection, fever, unexplained_weight_loss.

Guidance template for test-sample

```
"Clinical Note:" + {note} + "\n Think step-by-step and
output the final json following the instructions"
```

Figure 8: Final guidance prompt: We provide a final guidance to the LLM for inference a test sample. The '{note}' is replaced with the test sample to obtain the final input to the LLM.